

THE ROLE OF PRADHAN MANTRI MUDRA YOJANA AND EMPOWERING WOMEN

Dr.N.GIRI

Assistant Professor, Department of Commerce
Nallamuthu Gounder Mahalingam College, Pollachi

Abstract

Globally, female entrepreneurs encounter several obstacles during their process of expansion and advancement. Ownership of property or other assets and difficult access to finance are found to be the main obstacles preventing women from underdeveloped nations from pursuing their business dreams. Microfinance appears to be a different approach to help with the issue of capital scarcity and promote the expansion of entrepreneurship. Although there are already a number of microfinance organizations operating in the market to provide the impoverished with simple funding, their efficacy is still up for debate. The Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana (PMMY), a scheme recently introduced by the Indian government, intends to support small and medium-sized businesses and finance those that are underfunded

Keywords: Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana, Women, Empowerment, Entrepreneurs

Introduction

The Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana (PMMY) is a flagship scheme launched by the Government of India in 2015 to provide collateral-free loans to micro and small enterprises. One of the key objectives of the PMMY is to promote women entrepreneurship and women's economic empowerment. The PMMY scheme has played a crucial role in improving women's access to formal sources of credit. By providing collateral-free loans, the scheme has enabled more women to start and grow their own businesses, overcoming the traditional barriers they faced in securing financing. The data shows that a significant percentage of PMMY loans are disbursed to women-owned enterprises, with women accounting for 54.3% of the total PMMY loan disbursement in 2022. This highlights the scheme's success in encouraging women to venture into entrepreneurship and become self-employed. The PMMY scheme has also contributed to improving financial inclusion for women by bringing them into the formal financial system. This not only provides them access to credit but also helps them build a credit history and establish financial relationships with banks and other financial institutions. Additionally, the scheme is often accompanied by skill development programs and training initiatives that help women acquire the necessary skills and knowledge to start

and manage their enterprises effectively, enhancing the chances of success for women-led businesses.

Objectives of the Study

- ✓ To examine the classification of Mudra loans
- ✓ To examine the Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana loans sanctioned
- ✓ To analyse Disbursement in Women Account

Review of Literature

1. **Pushpender Kumar and et.al (2021)** made a study on “**Empowering women through Entrepreneurship, the Role of Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana**”. The objectives of the study states To examine the impact of Mudra loan on different indicators of women empowerment. The finding of the study states that the Mudra loan is promoting growth and development
2. **Tarak N. Sahu, and et.al (2021)** the study highlights the significance of MUDRA scheme, recognized as a potent poverty alleviation strategy, demonstrates its potential to uplift women in society traditionally dominated by men. The PMMY scheme has been instrumental in enhancing the livelihoods of women, fostering income generating sources, and contributing to their financial, social, and psychological development.
3. **Dr. Dattatry R Mane and et.al (2021)** made a study on “**Mudra Yojana: A Step towards Creating Growth for Women Entrepreneurs in Micro Enterprises Sector**”. The objectives of the study states that to evaluate the role of Mudra Yojana in Women Entrepreneurship Development”. The Findings of the study states that found that the share of amount sanctioned was higher in FY 2015-16 for women than the men counterparts, which gradually declined in the subsequent finance.
4. **Yogesh Mahajan (2021)**, has studied the impact of Mudra loans on small businesses. The enterprises are benefitted from no collateral loans but the conclusion was, there was no impact on the standard of living and financial independence has not achieved by the women entrepreneurs.
5. **DivyaMahadule and et.al (2022)** made a study on “**Impact of Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana on Women Entrepreneurs- a Comprehensive Review**”. The objective of the Study is to assess the Mudra Yojana components that benefit women the most. The study concluded that the Government is assisting women

entrepreneurs by providing financial and other Support such as Counseling, training and Skill Development.

Classification of Mudra Loan

The government of India's flagship program for providing micro and small businesses with inexpensive finance is the Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana, or PMMY. Mudra plans aim to "fund the unfunded," or integrate businesses into the established financial system. Loans under the PM Mudra lending plan are offered to micro and small, non-farm businesses that generate revenue through trading, manufacturing, and services. Government of India to launch one such programme called Pradhan Mantri Mudra, Yojana (PMMY) to provide easy access to funds for setting up enterprises. The scheme was launched on 8th April 2015 with the motive to 'fund the unfunded' with minimal formal complications and procedures. It provides easy, collateral-free loans to people who are interested in running small and medium enterprises which require maximum capital of Rs 10 lakh.¹ In a way, this scheme is a channel to encourage women of our country to take up entrepreneurship and overcome their social and economic barriers by offering those loans without any collateral and hassle-free application process. The PMMY scheme offers three types of products depending upon the financial requirement. The basic product 'Shishu' offers a loan of maximum of Rs. 50,000. In case, the financial requirement is higher than Rs 50,000 but less than Rs 5 lakh then 'Kishor' product is a suitable option. People can opt for another product called 'Tarun', if their financial need is more than Rs 5 lakh but less than Rs 10 lakh.

(Source: Author own Compilation)

Research Methodology

This study employs a descriptive research design to investigate the empowerment of women through entrepreneurship development under the MUDRA scheme in India. Data for this research is exclusively collected from secondary sources, including academic journals, research papers, the MSME Annual Reports, newspaper, books, Government websites and magazines. It provide qualitative insight into the personal and societal effects of women entrepreneurial journey.

Number of Mudra Loan Sanctioned from 2016-2023

(Source: sbi.co.in)

PMMY (Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana) loans sanctioned over the financial years from FY16 to FY23. The PMMY scheme is a government initiative to provide loans to small businesses and entrepreneurs. The key insights from the graph are:

1. The number of PMMY loans sanctioned has steadily increased from 3.97 crore in FY16 to a peak of 6.23 crore in FY23.
2. There was a significant jump in the number of loans sanctioned from 4.81 crore in FY18 to 5.99 crore in FY19.
3. The number of loans sanctioned remained above 5 crore for the last 5 financial years, from FY19 to FY23.
4. The highest number of loans sanctioned was in FY22 at 6.20 crore, followed by a slight decrease to 6.23 crore in FY23.

(Source: *sbi.co.in*)

Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana (PMMY) loans over the financial years from FY16 to FY23

1. The amount disbursed under PMMY loans has steadily increased from Rs. 1.33 lakh crore in FY16 to Rs. 4.50 lakh crore in FY23.
2. There was a significant jump in the amount disbursed from Rs. 2.46 lakh crore in FY18 to Rs. 3.11 lakh crore in FY19.
3. The amount disbursed remained above Rs. 3 lakh crore for the last 5 financial years, from FY19 to FY23.
4. The highest amount disbursed was in FY23 at Rs. 4.50 lakh crore, indicating a continuous growth in the funds provided under the PMMY scheme.

Disbursement in Women Account

(Source: sbi.co.in)

The disbursement in women's accounts under the PMMY (Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana) scheme, broken down by the three product categories: Shishu, Kishore, and Tarun. The data is presented as a percentage share for each product-wise category from 2016 to 2022.

1. Shishu, the smallest loan category, had the highest percentage share of disbursement in women's accounts, ranging from 72.8% in 2019 to 84.6% in 2017.
2. Kishore, the medium loan category, had the second-highest percentage share, starting at 13.7% in 2016 and increasing to 41.8% in 2022.
3. Tarun, the largest loan category, had the lowest percentage share, fluctuating between 4.0% in 2022 and 6.1% in 2016.
4. The percentage share of disbursement in women's accounts for all three categories has been decreasing over the years, with Shishu declining the most and Kishore increasing the most.
5. The overall trend shows a gradual shift in the distribution of PMMY loans towards women, with the Kishore category experiencing the most growth in its share.

Conclusion

The Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana (PMMY) has emerged as a transformative initiative that has significantly contributed to the empowerment of women in India. Through its multifaceted approach, the scheme has addressed the longstanding challenges faced by women entrepreneurs, enabling them to access crucial financial resources and support. The data clearly highlights the scheme's success in directing a substantial portion of its loan disbursements towards women-owned enterprises, with the Shishu category, which offers the smallest loans, being particularly effective in targeting women. This targeted focus has been instrumental in cultivating an environment that encourages and supports women to venture into entrepreneurship, ultimately fostering their economic independence and self-reliance. Moreover, the PMMY's role in improving financial inclusion for women has been pivotal. By bringing them into the formal banking system, the scheme has not only provided them with access to credit but has also helped them establish financial histories and relationships, further strengthening their position in the economic landscape. The complementary skill development and training programs integrated within the PMMY framework have further bolstered the capabilities of women entrepreneurs, equipping them with the necessary knowledge and skills to establish and manage their businesses effectively. As the PMMY continues to evolve and expand its reach, it is imperative that policymakers

maintain a strong focus on women's participation and explore innovative strategies to amplify the scheme's impact on women's empowerment. By building on the solid foundation laid by the PMMY, India can unlock the immense potential of its women entrepreneurs, fostering inclusive and sustainable economic growth for the nation.

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